

Online Supplement: Search-based Diverse Sampling From Real-world Software Product Lines

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S-1 Theoretical analysis on effects of δ

The distance metric is given as follows.

$$d_{ij} = d(x_i, x_j) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{\text{abs}(\mathcal{T}(x_i) - \mathcal{T}(x_j))}{n} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{|x_i \cap x_j|}{n} \right) \cdot \delta \quad (1)$$

where

$$\delta = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}} & \mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j) \leq n, \\ \frac{1}{n - \min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Theoretically, this setting of δ can mitigate bias towards sampling specific configurations. The following is our detailed analysis. We consider the following two cases.

Case 1: $\mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j) \leq n$. In this case, we have the following.

$$\begin{aligned} \min(|x_i \cap x_j|) &= n - (\mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j)) \\ \max(|x_i \cap x_j|) &= \min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\} + (n - \max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Further,

$$\begin{aligned} \min(|x_i \cap x_j|/n) &= 1 - \frac{\mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j)}{n} \\ \max(|x_i \cap x_j|/n) &= \frac{\min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} + \left(1 - \frac{\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \min(1 - |x_i \cap x_j|/n) &= \frac{\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} - \frac{\min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} \geq 0 \\ \max(1 - |x_i \cap x_j|/n) &= \frac{\mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j)}{n} \leq \frac{2 \max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

That is to say,

$$1 - \frac{|x_i \cap x_j|}{n} \in \left[0, \frac{2 \max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} \right]. \quad (6)$$

It can be found that the maximum value of $1 - \frac{|x_i \cap x_j|}{n}$ (i.e., the Hamming distance) is related to $\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}$. This potentially introduces biases. If two configurations with larger $\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}$, then their Hamming distance is potentially larger as well. In this case, these configurations are emphasized over those with less $\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}$ (as discussed in the main text, the novelty search algorithm prefers individuals with large novelty scores). For example, suppose that $\mathcal{T}(x_1) = 9$, $\mathcal{T}(x_2) = 10$, $\mathcal{T}(x_3) = 99$, $\mathcal{T}(x_4) = 100$, the pairs $\{x_1, x_2\}$ and $\{x_3, x_4\}$ have the same distances in the behaviors space, i.e., $1/2n$. However, the largest possible Hamming distance in the configuration space is $\frac{2*10}{n}$ and $\frac{2*100}{n}$ for the two pairs, respectively. Therefore, $\{x_3, x_4\}$ is potentially emphasized over $\{x_1, x_2\}$, leading to a bias in the behavior space. To mitigate this bias, δ is set to $\frac{1}{\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}$ to make the second part in Eq. (1) unrelated to $\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}$.

Case 2: $\mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j) > n$. In this case,

$$\begin{aligned} \min |x_i \cap x_j| &= \mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j) - n \\ \max |x_i \cap x_j| &= \min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\} + (n - \max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Based on similar deductions as in **Case 1**, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \min(1 - |x_i \cap x_j|/n) &= \frac{\max\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} - \frac{\min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} \geq 0 \\ \max(1 - |x_i \cap x_j|/n) &= 2 - \frac{\mathcal{T}(x_i) + \mathcal{T}(x_j)}{n} \leq 2 - \frac{2 \min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}{n} = \frac{2}{n}(n - \min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Therefore,

$$1 - \frac{|x_i \cap x_j|}{n} \in \left[0, \frac{2}{n}(n - \min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}) \right]. \quad (9)$$

Taking the above example again, $\{x_1, x_2\}$ is potentially emphasized over $\{x_3, x_4\}$ in this case. Similarly, δ is set to $\frac{1}{n - \min\{\mathcal{T}(x_i), \mathcal{T}(x_j)\}}$ to mitigate potential biases.

S-2 Parameter study on k

In NSbS, k is an important parameter which determines how many configurations in the archive are used to calculate the novelty score. To investigate the impact of this parameter, we consider six values for k , i.e., 2, 15, 25, 50, 75 and 100. Notice that 2 is the minimum possible value for k . When $k = 2$, the novelty score of a configuration is evaluated based on its two closest neighbors (including itself). The value 15 has been widely employed in NS-related literature [1], while values 25, 50, 75 and 100 are 1/4, 1/2, 3/4 and 4/4 of the sample size (i.e., 100), respectively. Testing multiple values of k allows us to observe the trend of the performance as k increases. Note that, to eliminate the impacts of initial population, the same set of configurations is initialized for all values of k in each of the 30 independent run.

Fig. S-1 presents, in the form of boxplots, *Spread* values over all runs on nine representative FMs. It can be found that $k \in \{50, 75, 100\}$ performs significantly worse than $k \in \{2, 15, 25\}$ on all FMs except lrzip and VP9. For the two models, values of k smaller than 100 have similar

Figure S-1: Parameter study on k in NSbS

performance, and they are all significantly better than 100. According to these results, k should be set to relatively small values, e.g., $k < 50$. Furthermore, it can be found that $k = 15$ yields the best performance on most of the feature models. Hence, $k = 15$ is advisable.

Finally, the following conclusions could be drawn based on the above parameter study experiment. *First, the performance of NSbS is indeed affected by its parameter k . In general, small values for k are preferred to large ones. Second, the value 15 is recommended for this parameter. That is to say, in the context of search-based diverse sampling, we can directly set k to the value that has been widely used in NS-related studies [1].*

S-3 Supplementary results

In this section, we provide some supplementary results in the form of either tables or figures.

Table S-1: Overview of the subject feature models

FM	$ \mathcal{F} $	$ \mathcal{C} $	$ \Psi $	$ core $	$ dead $	$ uc $
lrzip	20	63	1.44E+ 02	2	0	0
LLVM	11	1	1.02E+ 03	1	0	10
X264	16	11	1.15E+ 03	3	0	7
Dune	17	16	2.34E+ 03	2	0	0
BerkeleyDBC	18	19	2.56E+ 03	2	0	7
HiPAcc	31	104	1.35E+ 04	1	0	0
JHipster	45	104	2.63E+ 04	7	0	0
Polly	40	100	4.00E+ 04	9	0	0
7z	44	210	6.86E+ 04	5	0	0
JavaGC	39	105	1.93E+ 05	7	0	0
VP9	42	104	2.16E+ 05	9	0	0
fiasco_17.10	234	1178	1.00E+ 10	7	6	7
axTLS_2.1.4	94	190	2.00E+ 12	4	0	2
fiasco	1638	5228	3.58E+ 14	49	964	6
toybox	544	1020	1.45E+ 17	4	365	0
axtls	684	2155	4.29E+ 20	3	381	0
uClibc-ng_1.0.29	269	1403	8.00E+ 26	14	0	37
toybox_0.7.5	316	106	1.40E+ 81	8	15	203
uCLinux	1850	2468	1.63E+ 91	7	1237	0
ref4955	1218	3099	8.20E+ 123	0	50	0
adderII	1276	3206	3.57E+ 125	0	37	0
ecos-icse11	1244	3146	4.97E+ 125	0	35	0
m5272c3	1323	3297	2.37E+ 125	0	43	0
pati	1248	3266	7.90E+ 126	0	47	0
olpce2294	1274	3881	8.19E+ 126	0	42	0
integrator_arm9	1267	50606	4.06E+ 129	0	44	0
at91sam7sek	1319	3963	9.45E+ 131	0	74	0
se77x9	1319	49937	1.20E+ 135	0	58	0
phycore229x	1360	4026	1.77E+ 136	0	89	0
busybox-1.18.0	6796	17836	8.50E+ 216	12	3939	0
busybox_1.28.0	998	962	1.30E+ 248	12	0	177
embtoolkit	23516	180511	2.10E+ 252	839	6561	1
freebsd-icse11	1396	62163	8.39E+ 313	3	38	50
uCLinux-config	11254	31637	7.78E+ 417	15	6012	0
buildroot	14910	45603	/	100	6895	12
freetz	31012	102705	/	117	14445	0
2.6.28.6-icse11	6888	343944	/	58	102	41
2.6.32-2var	60072	268223	/	1100	31960	12
2.6.33.3-2var	62482	273799	/	1200	33233	12

Table S-2: Means of *Spread* and novelty score obtained by using two different distance metrics

	Spread		Novelty score	
	<i>Weighted</i> distance	<i>Unweighted</i> distance	<i>Weighted</i> distance	<i>Unweighted</i> distance
lrzip	2.0526e + 00	2.0526e + 00‡	9.9133e + 00	1.0000e + 01◦
LLVM	4.5455e - 02	0.0000e + 00◦	2.0524e + 01	2.0106e + 01●
X264	9.2857e - 01	9.2857e - 01‡	1.7804e + 01	1.7233e + 01●
Dune	2.1250e + 00	2.1250e + 00‡	2.0243e + 01	1.9561e + 01●
BerkeleyDBC	1.8235e + 00	1.8235e + 00‡	1.9072e + 01	1.7596e + 01●
HiPAcc	3.9677e + 00	3.9677e + 00‡	1.6882e + 01	1.6511e + 01●
JHipster	4.1795e + 00	4.1795e + 00‡	1.4126e + 01	1.3621e + 01●
Polly	6.8125e + 00	6.8125e + 00‡	1.7736e + 01	1.6701e + 01●
7z	1.2650e + 01	1.2650e + 01‡	1.3269e + 01	1.2302e + 01●
JavaGC	7.6364e + 00	7.6364e + 00‡	1.8512e + 01	1.7561e + 01●
VP9	8.5000e + 00	8.5000e + 00‡	1.9341e + 01	1.8484e + 01●
fiasco_17_10	6.5065e + 01	6.5063e + 01‡	8.3322e + 00	8.0510e + 00●
axtls_2.1.4	3.6923e + 00	3.7143e + 00●	1.8642e + 01	1.8107e + 01●
fiasco	9.2354e + 01	9.2806e + 01‡	3.8041e + 00	3.6524e + 00●
toybox	8.3438e + 00	8.2727e + 00‡	7.3089e + 00	6.9995e + 00●
axTLS	2.8098e + 01	2.8098e + 01‡	8.6808e + 00	8.4600e + 00●
uClibc-ng_1.0.29	2.9381e + 01	2.9348e + 01‡	1.8690e + 01	1.7970e + 01●
toybox_0.7.5	2.8184e + 01	2.8197e + 01‡	3.2225e + 01	3.1474e + 01●
uCLinux	1.6491e + 01	1.8036e + 01‡	1.2095e + 01	1.1966e + 01‡
ref4955	7.0180e + 00	7.7938e + 00‡	1.8203e + 01	1.7809e + 01‡
adderII	6.4673e + 00	7.1895e + 00‡	1.8458e + 01	1.8115e + 01‡
ecos-icse11	7.3669e + 00	7.2504e + 00‡	1.8664e + 01	1.7968e + 01●
m5272c3	7.5453e + 00	8.1155e + 00‡	1.8105e + 01	1.7630e + 01●
pati	7.0133e + 00	7.0537e + 00‡	1.8118e + 01	1.8054e + 01‡
olpce2294	7.7616e + 00	7.3163e + 00‡	1.8423e + 01	1.7990e + 01‡
integrator_arm9	8.4579e + 00	7.4967e + 00‡	1.8693e + 01	1.8010e + 01●
at91sam7sek	7.9485e + 00	7.7105e + 00‡	1.8269e + 01	1.7920e + 01●
se77x9	7.5404e + 00	7.4208e + 00‡	1.8184e + 01	1.7540e + 01●
phycore229x	7.5967e + 00	7.1922e + 00‡	1.8238e + 01	1.7773e + 01●
busybox-1.18.0	2.8263e + 02	2.8317e + 02‡	1.0421e + 01	1.0331e + 01‡
busybox_1.28.0	1.2128e + 01	1.2160e + 01‡	2.5628e + 01	2.5557e + 01‡
embtoolkit	2.1704e + 03	2.1633e + 03‡	1.2476e + 01	1.2408e + 01‡
freebsd-icse11	2.0491e + 01	1.9458e + 01‡	2.0570e + 01	2.0334e + 01●
uCLinux-config	4.0272e + 02	4.0315e + 02‡	9.7661e + 00	9.6931e + 00‡
buildroot	3.1025e + 02	3.1381e + 02●	1.1541e + 01	1.1294e + 01●
freetz	1.3418e + 03	1.3422e + 03‡	7.7830e + 00	7.4249e + 00●
2.6.28.6-icse11	4.9075e + 01	5.0597e + 01‡	2.0740e + 01	2.0666e + 01‡
2.6.32-2var	1.7504e + 03	1.7504e + 03‡	1.1937e + 01	1.1966e + 01‡
2.6.33.3-2var	1.7242e + 03	1.7716e + 03●	1.1913e + 01	1.1985e + 01◦

Table S-3: Means of *Spread* obtained by NSbS (with δ) and NSbS- δ (without δ)

	NSbS	NSbS- δ
lrzip	2.0526e + 00	2.0526e + 00‡
LLVM	4.5455e - 02	9.0909e - 02‡
X264	9.2857e - 01	9.2857e - 01‡
Dune	2.1250e + 00	2.1250e + 00‡
BerkeleyDBC	1.8235e + 00	1.8235e + 00‡
HiPAcc	3.9677e + 00	4.0000e + 00●
JHipster	4.1795e + 00	4.2051e + 00●
Polly	6.8125e + 00	6.8125e + 00‡
7z	1.2650e + 01	1.2650e + 01‡
JavaGC	7.6364e + 00	7.6364e + 00‡
VP9	8.5000e + 00	8.5000e + 00‡
fiasco_17_10	6.5065e + 01	6.5108e + 01‡
axtls_2_1_4	3.6923e + 00	4.0275e + 00●
fiasco	9.2354e + 01	9.2667e + 01‡
toybox	8.3438e + 00	8.8409e + 00●
axTLS	2.8098e + 01	2.8860e + 01●
uClibc-ng_1_0_29	2.9381e + 01	2.9777e + 01‡
toybox_0_7_5	2.8184e + 01	2.9082e + 01‡
uClinux	1.6491e + 01	1.8830e + 01‡
ref4955	7.0180e + 00	1.4699e + 01●
adderII	6.4673e + 00	1.6448e + 01●
ecos-icse11	7.3669e + 00	1.5880e + 01●
m5272c3	7.5453e + 00	1.2575e + 01●
pati	7.0133e + 00	1.4337e + 01●
olpce2294	7.7616e + 00	1.5767e + 01●
integrator_arm9	8.4579e + 00	1.5282e + 01●
at91sam7sek	7.9485e + 00	1.4910e + 01●
se77x9	7.5404e + 00	1.6196e + 01●
phycore229x	7.5967e + 00	1.7005e + 01●
busybox-1.18.0	2.8263e + 02	2.9572e + 02●
busybox_1_28_0	1.2128e + 01	2.4733e + 01●
embtoolkit	2.1704e + 03	2.2095e + 03●
freebsd-icse11	2.0491e + 01	3.7382e + 01●
uClinux-config	4.0272e + 02	4.3660e + 02●
buildroot	3.1025e + 02	3.3896e + 02●
freetz	1.3418e + 03	1.4399e + 03●
2.6.28.6-icse11	4.9075e + 01	1.5158e + 02●
2.6.32-2var	1.7504e + 03	1.8503e + 03●
2.6.33.3-2var	1.7242e + 03	1.8848e + 03●

Table S-4: Means of *Spread* for each sampler on each feature model. ‘N/A’ indicates that results are not available due to a timeout

FM	NSbS	SAT-based	DDBs	Unigen3	Smarch
lrzip	2.0526e + 00	2.0526e + 00‡	2.0526e + 00‡	2.0526e + 00‡	2.0526e + 00‡
LLVM	4.5455e - 02	3.6364e - 01●	0.0000e + 00◦	5.4545e - 01●	2.2727e - 01●
X264	9.2857e - 01	1.2143e + 00●	9.2857e - 01‡	9.2857e - 01‡	1.1429e + 00●
Dune	2.1250e + 00	2.1250e + 00‡	2.1250e + 00‡	3.5625e + 00●	2.1250e + 00●
BerkeleyDBC	1.8235e + 00	2.2941e + 00●	1.8235e + 00‡	2.0000e + 00●	2.0000e + 00●
HiPAcc	3.9677e + 00	4.0323e + 00●	3.9677e + 00‡	7.2903e + 00●	5.1613e + 00●
JHipster	4.1795e + 00	4.2051e + 00●	4.1795e + 00‡	6.2821e + 00●	5.4872e + 00●
Polly	6.8125e + 00	6.8125e + 00‡	6.8125e + 00‡	6.8125e + 00‡	6.8125e + 00‡
7z	1.2650e + 01	1.2650e + 01‡	1.2650e + 01‡	1.2650e + 01‡	1.2650e + 01‡
JavaGC	7.6364e + 00	7.6364e + 00‡	7.6364e + 00‡	7.6364e + 00‡	7.6364e + 00‡
VP9	8.5000e + 00	8.5000e + 00‡	8.5000e + 00‡	8.5000e + 00‡	8.5000e + 00‡
fiasco_17.10	6.5065e + 01	6.5090e + 01‡	N/A	7.1631e + 01●	6.9739e + 01●
axTLS_2.1.4	3.6923e + 00	4.0055e + 00●	N/A	1.2846e + 01●	1.2527e + 01●
fiasco	9.2354e + 01	9.5273e + 01●	N/A	1.1354e + 02●	1.4046e + 02●
toybox	8.3438e + 00	9.6335e + 00●	N/A	3.0295e + 01●	2.8426e + 01●
axtls	2.8098e + 01	2.8608e + 01●	N/A	6.1934e + 01●	6.4548e + 01●
uClibc-ng_1.0.29	2.9381e + 01	2.9842e + 01‡	N/A	5.2809e + 01●	5.4002e + 01●
toybox_0.7.5	2.8184e + 01	2.8344e + 01‡	N/A	5.5333e + 01●	5.3199e + 01●
uCLinux	1.6491e + 01	5.5825e + 01●	N/A	1.0439e + 02●	1.0942e + 02●
ref4955	7.0180e + 00	2.6317e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.6240e + 02●
adderII	6.4673e + 00	2.9283e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.8470e + 02●
ecos-icse11	7.3669e + 00	2.8403e + 01●	N/A	N/A	N/A
m5272c3	7.5453e + 00	2.1888e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.7890e + 02●
pati	7.0133e + 00	2.8496e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.8119e + 02●
olpce2294	7.7616e + 00	2.8532e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.9046e + 02●
integrator_arm9	8.4579e + 00	3.2970e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.7845e + 02●
at91sam7sek	7.9485e + 00	3.0774e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.6643e + 02●
se77x9	7.5404e + 00	2.6939e + 01●	N/A	N/A	N/A
phycore229x	7.5967e + 00	3.0151e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.8180e + 02●
busybox-1.18.0	2.8263e + 02	3.1111e + 02●	N/A	N/A	N/A
busybox_1.28.0	1.2128e + 01	6.3088e + 01●	N/A	N/A	2.0145e + 02●
embtoolkit	2.1704e + 03	2.2417e + 03●	N/A	N/A	N/A
freebsd-icse11	2.0491e + 01	8.3536e + 01●	N/A	N/A	N/A
uCLinux-config	4.0272e + 02	4.8453e + 02●	N/A	N/A	N/A
buildroot	3.1025e + 02	3.9200e + 02●	N/A	N/A	N/A
freetz	1.3418e + 03	1.6547e + 03●	N/A	N/A	N/A
2.6.28.6-icse11	4.9075e + 01	4.0089e + 02●	N/A	N/A	N/A
2.6.32-2var	1.7504e + 03	2.0404e + 03●	N/A	N/A	N/A
2.6.33.3-2var	1.7242e + 03	2.2249e + 03●	N/A	N/A	N/A

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